

Influence of particulate size on creep properties of TiB-reinforced orthorhombic Ti-22Al-27Nb

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SUMMARY: Orthorhombic titanium alloys based on the intermetallic phase Ti₂AlNb exhibit a higher strength and stiffness at temperatures above 500°C compared to conventional titanium alloys and a higher ductility than γ -TiAl intermetallics. However, the creep resistance needs to be improved. Therefore, attempts have been made to reinforce the known Ti-22Al-27Nb (at.-%) by titanium boride (TiB) particulates. Different processing routes allow the production of composites with varying TiB particulate size. The volume fraction of particulates has been kept constant at 6.5%. In this study the influence of particulate size on the steady state creep rate has been examined in the temperature range from 650°C to 700°C. The steady state creep rate 8 μ m TiB particulates is about one third of the steady state creep rate of the material with 40 μ m TiB particulates.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composites, particulate reinforcement, titanium, intermetallics, orthorhombic, creep.

INTRODUCTION

Titanium alloys are standard materials for aeroengine compressors. To extend the application region of titanium alloys, new systems are under development. Promising candidates are orthorhombic alloys based on the intermetallic phase Ti₂AlNb [1, 2]. These extend the application temperature to 650 or 700°C, which is about 100°C higher than advanced conventional alloys, such as Timetal 834. Additionally, the ductility and fracture toughness is much better compared to intermetallics based on γ -TiAl [3]. The strength and stiffness at elevated temperatures are acceptable, but the creep resistance must be improved. To improve this property three possible methods are under development: (i) microstructural modification [4], (ii) modification of alloy composition [5] and (iii) particulate reinforcement. In this study the reinforcement by titanium boride particulates is investigated. The effect of TiB particulate reinforcement on tensile and fatigue properties has been reported recently [6, 7]. Different processing routes allow the production of composites with varying particulate size. This work investigates the influence of the particulate size on the creep properties of 6.5% TiB-reinforced Ti-22Al-27Nb. The percentage is expressed in weight-% as well as volume-%, since the density of TiB and the matrix is nearly the same. Within the focus of this study the steady state creep rate, activation energy, and primary creep data were obtained.

PRODUCTION OF MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

To obtain TiB particulate reinforced Ti-22Al-27Nb, a boron containing Ti-22Al-27Nb alloy ingot with a diameter of 50 mm was prepared by plasma arc melting. The particulates were formed by in-situ reaction of B and Ti during solidification. Due to slow cooling rate of the ingot large TiB particulates grew. Under the assumption that all B atoms react with Ti atoms to form TiB, a mass fraction of 6.5% TiB was calculated. For the first series of specimens the ingot was hot rolled into 11.8 mm square bars, annealed at 1150°C in the B2 single-phase region for one hour followed by slow cooling, and then aged at 850°C in the (O + B2) two phase region for 33 hours followed by air cooling to stabilize the matrix microstructure. This composite material will be designated as ingot material (IM). Figure 1 shows SEM images of the microstructure of the IM material. Large particulates are aligned in the rolling direction. Particulate lengths are about 40 μm with a diameter of about 5 μm . Cylindrical specimens with a gauge length of 22 mm and a diameter of 4 mm were machined from this material.

Figure 1: Microstructure of IM material transverse (left) and longitudinal (right) to the rolling direction (horizontal).

For the second series, composites with same chemical composition were produced using the gas-atomized powder metallurgy method (PM). To produce gas-atomized powder, the plasma arc-melted ingot has been remelted by a high frequency induction coil. The boron was redissolved into the melt. Simultaneously, a high speed argon gas jet bombarded the melt and atomized it into a very fine spherical powder. Again, the B atoms react with the Ti atoms to form TiB particulates in the powder during solidification. Due to the high cooling rate of the powder, the size of the TiB particulates is extremely small. Fully densified bulk material was produced by hot isostatic pressing at 200 MPa and 1100°C for 3 hours in a steel capsule with a diameter of 46 mm. The material was then hot rolled and heat treated as described above for the IM material. The smaller particulate size of the PM material in Fig. 2 is apparent. The particles are aligned in rolling direction similar to the IM material. The length of the particulates is about 5 μm and the diameter is about 1 μm .

Figure 2: Microstructure of PM material transverse (left) and longitudinal (right) to the rolling direction (horizontal).

Creep tests have been carried out to determine the steady state creep rate of secondary creep at 650, 675 and 700°C. The specimens were loaded at a constant stress. After a distinct primary phase, the slope of the strain-time diagram becomes constant. When the slope stabilizes for a certain time, the steady state creep rate (SSCR) was determined and the stress was increased to the next stress level (fig. 3). Again, a short primary phase appears. When the strain or strain rate was too high, the creep rate develops into the tertiary phase and the experiment was aborted.

Figure 3: Scheme of the experimental procedure by stepwise loading.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 4 shows a typical result. The experiment starts with distinct primary creep and develops a constant slope. When the time was sufficient to determine the steady state creep rate, the stress was increased by 50 MPa. In this diagram, the difference between the PM and IM material is apparent. To define the transition from primary to secondary creep, the primary fraction of the creep strain has been displayed in a strain-time plot by subtracting the secondary fraction of the total strain. When the primary fraction does not increase, transition takes place.

Figure 4: Typical strain-time plot. The load was stepwise increased and the temperature was kept constant at 675°C.

Using the strain-time plot, the time to reach a given strain can be determined. In fig. 5 the time for a creep strain of 0.5% at a constant load of 150 MPa is compared. In some cases, especially for the PM material, the time was determined by extrapolation of the experimental values. It can be seen that the time to 0.5% strain is three to four times longer for the PM material compared to the IM material. This value considers primary as well as secondary creep and is of practical relevance.

Figure 5: Comparison of time needed for 0.5% creep strain at 150 MPa.

The main objective of this study was to determine the steady state creep rate and the activation energy for creep. A summary of the steady state creep rates can be found in fig. 6. A significant reduction of the creep rate of the PM material compared to the IM material is visible. Considering a constant creep rate the stress can be increased by about 50 MPa or the temperature can be increased by about 25°C using the PM material instead of the IM material. Remarkably the creep rate of the IM material does not increase with increasing stress at high stresses. Causes for this phenomenon are not yet known.

Figure 6: Steady state creep rate of PM and IM material as function of load and temperature.

Creep rate versus stress data in fig. 6 were used to determine the activation energy, which strong stress dependence (fig. 7 left). The activation energy of IM and PM material is comparable. The activation energy for 300 MPa is abnormally low; this is also seen in fig. 6. The relatively low activation energy at 150 MPa may mark grain boundary diffusion. There seems to be a transition at about 150 MPa to dislocation climb. The stress exponent below 150 MPa (fig. 7 right) is very low. Usual values are close to unity. For 150 MPa and above, the values are in the usual range from 3.5 to 5. A creep exponent greater than 3.5 suggests dislocation climb [8] which confirms the assumption made by the activation energy.

Figure 7: Activation energy (left) and stress exponent (right) determined by the experiments results.

The improvement of creep resistance by the smaller particulates of the PM material compared to the IM material is apparent. Considering the same creep rate, the percentage increase of allowed stress for the PM material is at least in the same order of magnitude as measured previously by tensile testing [7]. A third series of specimens with medium sized particulates were produced by heat treatment after rolling. It showed an even smaller creep rate than the PM material presented here. These experiments are not finished yet and results will be published soon. It is not yet possible to conclude that smaller particulates result in an improved behaviour in general. Future work must be completed and TiB morphology must be studied to determine the optimum size and amount of TiB.

Analysis of the microdamage after creep showed distinct formation of voids at the grain boundaries of the B2 primary grains and debonding at the ends of the TiB particulates for the IM material. The PM material also showed voids at the boundaries of the B2 primary grains, but debonding at the particulates was not observed. Specimens tested under long-term conditions showed some surface cracks initiated by the brittle oxide scale. These cracks arrested around of a few hundred of microns.

CONCLUSIONS

TiB particulate reinforced Ti-22Al-27Nb composites can be produced by addition of boron to the molten ingot. The in-situ grown ellipsoidal particulates are relatively large with a length up to 40 μm and a diameter of about 5 μm . TiB particulate reinforced Ti-22Al-27Nb composites with smaller particulates can be produced by gas atomized powder. This material contains particulates with a maximum length of 5 μm and a diameter less than 1 μm . Primary as well as secondary creep behaviour is significantly improved by the material based on gas atomized powder compared to the ingot material. Smaller particulates seem to be more effective in blocking of dislocation climb. Due to the higher surface-to-volume ratio of smaller particulates these are less sensitive to debonding mechanisms. However, the assumption that particulates as better as smaller cannot be confirmed. Medium sized particulate reinforced composites showed an even better behaviour than material with small sized particulates.

In general the improvement of the creep resistance by particulate reinforcement is not as high as that of new developed quaternary orthorhombic alloys (e.g. Ti-22Al-20Nb-2W) without reinforcement [9]. As a consequence the solution may be the particulate reinforcement of such an advanced alloy.

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